

Description of the consensus meetings process used to adapt the World Health Organization framework for the quality of Maternal and Newborn Health Care for Post-Abortion Care in the AMoCo study.

AMoCo (Abortion-related Morbidity and mortality in fragile and Conflict settings) study

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Introduction

The main objective of the AMoCo (Abortion-related Morbidity and mortality in fragile and Conflict settings) study was to describe and estimate the burden of abortion-related complications in hospitals supported by Médecins Sans Frontières (MSF) in African humanitarian settings. The study protocol, including study design, detailed procedures, sampling, informed consent processes and other ethical considerations, is available on MSF's scientific portal(1) and is registered with ClinicalTrials.gov NCT04331847. The main results of this study have been published and describe the magnitude and severity of abortion-related complications in two referral hospitals in humanitarian settings: one in Bangui in the Central African Republic (CAR) and the other in Jigawa State in northern Nigeria(2). This article also provides a detailed description of these two settings.

One of the secondary objectives of this study was to assess the quality of post-abortion care (PAC) provided in the referral hospitals studied. Quality of care is a multi-dimensional concept(3,4) making it difficult to measure comprehensively. The Donabedian model(3) is frequently used to operationalize the definition of quality because it is widely accepted as encompassing the main components of health care quality(5). It includes three dimensions: structure or inputs to care; process of care; and (health) outcomes of care. Several quality-of-care frameworks incorporating the three Donabedian dimensions have been developed to drive quality improvement processes(6), including for maternal care(4,7–9) and safe abortion care(10,11). The World Health Organization (WHO) conceptual framework for maternal and newborn health care (MNHC) extends the Donabedian's model by dividing the process of care into the provision of care by health professionals and women's experience of care to emphasize the importance of people-centered care(4). However, to our knowledge, at the time the study was designed, there was no published framework for measuring the quality of PAC and the WHO framework for MNHC did not include quality measurement indicators for PAC. Therefore, the AMoCo study technical steering committee collaboratively modified some elements of the WHO quality of care framework for MNHC(4) to measure PAC quality in hospitals through a consensus process(12,13).

The objective of this technical note is to describe the consensus process used to adapt the WHO quality of care framework for MNHC(4) to measure PAC quality in hospitals.

Description of the consensus process:

The quality-of-care framework to be used and the corresponding PAC indicators were chosen using a consensus meetings process(12,13), implementing two in-person meetings, literature reviews and working groups that exchanged by emails or Visio conferences. We created a technical steering committee for the study by choosing members of the study partners' organizations with research experience, clinical backgrounds, clinical experience in hospitals of humanitarian settings and/or experience in measuring quality of at least one component of comprehensive abortion care (contraception, safe abortion care and post-abortion care).

During the first in-person meeting (June 2018), the technical steering committee identified the WHO framework for the quality of MNHC(4) as a relevant framework to be adapted for PAC. This framework was chosen because this is a maternal health comprehensive framework that nonetheless encompasses the three dimensions of the Donabedian model but also emphasizes the importance of a person-centered approach. It includes eleven quality domains: competent human resources, essential physical resources, functional referral systems, coverage of key medical practices, actionable information system, evidence-based practices, effective communication, respect and preservation of

dignity, emotional support as well as health and person-centered outcomes(4). At this meeting, we also brainstormed a potential list of indicators for each of the eleven domains. Next, we divided the members of the technical steering group in subgroups and assigned different teams to work on these domains.

Four members did a literature review to identify existing indicators for PAC for each domain (cf. search strategy below). EP and OO investigated indicators of essential physical resources, functional referral systems, coverage of key medical practices, actionable information system, evidence-based practices, effective communication, respect and preservation of dignity, emotional support as well as health and person-centered outcomes. TF and BP investigated indicators of knowledge, attitudes, practices, and behavior (KAPB) of health professionals (competent human resources). During this literature review, for each domain, existing indicators and corresponding questions/questionnaires were listed with their characteristics. The following characteristics were searched: their face, construct (using for example the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin statistic) & criterion (logically correlated with another measure of the same topic) validity, their reliability (Cronbach alpha) in English and French, their use in sub-Saharan African contexts (the number of countries where it was used and the number of published studies in such context), the time needed to collect the data and the price to be able to use it (cf. table 1 below). The WHO team of the WHO Multi-Country Study on Abortion(14) gave us copies of their data collection tools that were not yet published during the AMoCo study design.

Thereafter, using this list of indicators/corresponding questions with their characteristics, draft data collection tools were developed by groups of members of the technical steering committee. When indicators or questions were not found in the literature (some indicators for health professionals' KAPB towards PAC and for evidence-based medical practices), the steering committee members developed the indicators and corresponding data collection items or questions using WHO(15) and Médecins Sans Frontières (MSF)(16) PAC guidelines (cf. table 1 below). Corresponding questions or items were included in four standardized data collection tools of four study components: 1) a health facility assessment, 2) a KAPB survey of health professionals, 3) a prospective medical record review of women presenting with abortion-related complications in the hospitals, and 4) a quantitative patient survey among a sub-sample of those women who stayed at least overnight. The detailed procedures of these four components can be found in the AMoCo study protocol in the MSF science portal(1). BP and CSH developed the facility assessment tool looking at essential human & physical resources and functional referral systems. TF and DL developed the questionnaire looking at knowledge, attitudes, practices, and behaviors of health professionals (competent human resources). EP, OO, and CF developed the case report form looking at indicators of coverage of key medical practices, actionable information system, evidence-based practices, and health-related outcomes. EP and TF developed the questionnaire looking at women's experience of care (effective communication, respect and preservation of dignity, emotional support) and person-centered outcome. The WHO team leading the WHO Multi-Country Study on Abortion(14) was consulted to provide advice on some indicators as part of this process.

During the second technical steering committee in-person meeting (April 2019), all data collection tools were reviewed with all members and indicators/corresponding questions were chosen by verbal consensus. All standardized data collection tools were developed in English, translated into French and back translated. The women's questionnaire was also translated in local languages and back translated into English (in Nigeria) or French (in CAR). All data collection tools, and corresponding procedures were pretested, piloted and revised. At data analysis and paper writing stages, EP completed the literature review to check if some indicators/questionnaires included in our study tools had been used, validated and/or completed since the study commenced. Last, final indicators were refined by the

steering committee members supported by external experts (VF, LB) that led to a reduction of the number of indicators and a reformulation of some of them (for e.g. we reworked the risk of healthcare-related abortion near-miss). We then modified the presentation of the eleven domains to align with the Donabedian model(3) from which the original WHO framework was created as we felt it was more intuitive to understand.

Figure 1 presents this quality framework with the eleven WHO domains and a total of 29 PAC quality measures. Table 1 details these 29 quality measures and its corresponding indicators with their characteristics found in the literature.

Literature reviews’ search strategy:

Questions:

- 1- What were the indicators used to assess PAC quality,
 - a. globally?
 - b. in low- and middle-income countries?
 - c. in Conflict/Fragile/Humanitarian/Displaced/Refugee settings?
- 2- What quality of PAC frameworks were developed or used?

Date: 05 March 2019

Key words search strategy	Limits	Results	Selected abstracts after title screening	Selected articles after title and abstract/full document screening
1- (post abortion[Title/Abstract] OR post-abortion[Title/Abstract] OR postabortion[Title/Abstract] OR miscarriage[Title/Abstract] OR "abortion-related complication*" [Title/Abstract] OR "abortion complication*" [Title/Abstract]) AND Quality[Title/Abstract] AND care[Title/Abstract]	5 years	119 results	23	22 + 9 from references & experts’ advice
2- ("signal functions" [Title/Abstract] AND (post abortion[Title/Abstract] OR post-abortion[Title/Abstract] OR postabortion[Title/Abstract] OR miscarriage[Title/Abstract] OR "abortion-related complication*" [Title/Abstract] OR "abortion complication*" [Title/Abstract]))	5 years	5 results	2 additional	
TOTAL			25	31 (11,14,25–34,17,35–44,18–24)
Among them, how many in humanitarian settings				4 (17–20)

Date: 09 March 2023 (new publications since 05 March 2019)

Key words search strategy	Limits	Results	Selected new abstracts after title screening	New selected articles after title and abstract/full document screening
3- (post abortion[Title/Abstract] OR post-abortion[Title/Abstract] OR postabortion[Title/Abstract] OR miscarriage[Title/Abstract] OR "abortion-related complication*" [Title/Abstract] OR "abortion complication*" [Title/Abstract]) AND Quality[Title/Abstract] AND care[Title/Abstract]	5 years	194 results	71	34 + 3 from references & experts' advice
4- ("post abortion"[Title/Abstract] OR post-abortion[Title/Abstract] OR postabortion[Title/Abstract] OR miscarriage[Title/Abstract]) AND ("conflict"[Title/Abstract] OR "displac*" [Title/Abstract] OR "refugee*" [Title/Abstract] OR "humanitar*" [Title/Abstract] OR "crisis" [Title/Abstract] OR "fragile")	5 years	87 results	17 additional	
TOTAL			88	37 (10,45,54–63,46,64–73,47,74–80,48–53)
Among them, how many in humanitarian settings				4 (45–47,79)

Figure 1: Framework for assessing the quality of PAC in hospitals, including 11 domains from the WHO framework on MNHC and 29 quality measures.

Table 1: Characteristics of the quality of PAC indicators and their corresponding items/questions or questionnaires found in the literature:

Quality measures and corresponding indicators by domains from WHO QoC framework for MNHC(4) measured in AMoCo study	Targets	Data source	English Reliability	English Validity (construct and criterion)	Used and adapted in English Speaking African countries	French reliability	French validity (construct and criterion)	Used and adapted in French Speaking African countries	Used in research studies	Time in interview/in data collection	Price	References
1- INPUTS/STRUCTURE												
<p>COMPETENT HUMAN RESOURCES: Adequate knowledge, attitudes & practices of health professionals</p> <p><i>Training & positive attitudes in PAC</i> Percentage of doctors, medical officers, midwives/nurses and midwifery/nurse assistant who are providing post-abortion care and who^a:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - have been trained in Post-Abortion Care - agreed that access to post-abortion care is every woman's right <p><i>Correct knowledge in management of key complications</i> Percentage of doctors, medical officers, midwives/nurses who are providing post-abortion care and who^a:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - knew the recommended misoprostol regimen to treat first trimester incomplete abortions - knew the recommended antibiotic regimen to treat septic abortions - reported using Dilatation & sharp Curetage (D&C) (non-recommended inappropriate technology) when treating incomplete abortion by instrumental uterine evacuation 	100% 100% 100% 100% 0%	Knowledge, Attitude Practice Behavior survey – Health professionals ^a	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Built from guidelines (16) and unpublished questionnaires
<p>HUMAN, PHYSICAL RESOURCES & REFERRAL SYSTEM: Extended comprehensive post-abortion care signal functions (Trained medical professionals on duty 24/7, infrastructure, Drugs, supplies & services for PAC and for contraception available): Percentage of the extended comprehensive post-abortion care signal functions (n=27) available in the facility (38,52)^b</p>	100%	Rapid Facility Assessment	NA	NA	Yes (11 countries)	NA	NA	Yes (8 countries including 1 humanitarian setting)	At least 14 studies	15 to 30 min	Free	Found in 2019 (28,30,37–39) Found in 2023 (51,56–58,63,69,70,79)

Quality measures and corresponding indicators measured in AMoCo study	Targets	Data source	English Reliability	English Validity (construct and criterion)	Used and adapted in English Speaking African countries	French reliability	French validity (construct and criterion)	Used and adapted in French Speaking African countries	Used in research studies	Time in interview/w/in data collection	Price	References
2- PROCESSES												
PROVISION OF CARE: Coverage of key practices												
<p>- <i>Uterine evacuation</i>: Percentage of women who received</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • instrumental uterine evacuation • uterine evacuation by uterotonics <p>- <i>Key interventions for severe complications</i>: Percentage of women who received</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • blood transfusion. • IV fluids • Intensive Care Unit admission • hysterectomies <p>- <i>Pain management</i>: Percentage of women who received analgesics</p>	NA	Prospective Medical Record Review (MRR)	NA	NA	Yes (5 countries)	NA	NA	Yes (5 countries including 1 humanitarian setting)	At least 1 multi country study	NA	Free	Found in 2019 (14)
- <i>Contraception uptake</i> : Percentage of women who received contraception at discharge			NA	NA	Yes (9 countries)	NA	NA	Yes (7 countries)	At least 12 studies	NA	Free	Found in 2019 (14,17–19,21,22,24,27,28,35) Found in 2023 (49,53,54,65,66,77–79)

Quality measures and corresponding indicators measured in AMoCo study	Targets	Data source	English Reliability	English Validity (construct and criterion)	Used and adapted in English Speaking African countries	French reliability	French validity (construct and criterion)	Used and adapted in French Speaking African countries	Used in research studies	Time in interview/in data collection	Price	References
2- PROCESSES (Follow-up)												
PROVISION OF CARE: Information system												
<i>Completeness of clinical medical records on key medical information:</i> Percentage of women with complete information in their medical records on key medical information: gestational age, vital signs, abdominal examination, cervix examination (proxy for gynecological exam), mental status and appearance at presentation & final diagnosis	100 %	MRR	NA	NA	Yes (5 countries)	NA	NA	Yes (5 countries including 1 humanitarian setting)	1 multicountry study	NA	Free	Found in 2019 (14) Found in 2023 (79)

Quality measures and corresponding indicators measured in AMoCo study	Targets	Data source	English Reliability	English Validity (construct and criterion)	Used and adapted in English Speaking African countries	French reliability	French validity (construct and criterion)	Used and adapted in French Speaking African countries	Used in research studies	Time in interview/in data collection	Price	References
2- PROCESSES (Follow-up)												
PROVISION OF CARE: Application of post-abortion care evidence-based clinical guidelines (practices):												
<i>Appropriate (preventative or curative) treatment for</i> - <i>Uterine evacuation</i> : Percentage of women undergoing Dilatation & sharp Curettage when having an instrumental uterine evacuation (inappropriate)	0%	MRR	NA	NA	Yes (7 countries)	NA	NA	Yes (6 countries)	14 studies	NA	Free	Found in 2019 (18,19,21,24,26,35,44) Found in 2023 (49,50,53,56,65-67,79)
- <i>Hemorrhage</i> : Percentage of women	100%		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Built from guidelines (15,16)
• receiving blood transfusion when indicated ^c			NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	
• receiving blood transfusion when there is no reported indication ^c (inappropriate)	0%		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	
- <i>Infections</i> : Percentage of women	100%	MRR	NA	NA	Yes (5 countries)	NA	NA	Yes (5 countries)	1 study	NA	Free	Found in 2019 (44) + built from guidelines (15,16) Found in 2023 (50)
• with septic abortion ^d receiving curative antibiotics			NA	NA	Yes (1 country)	NA	NA	NA	1 study	NA	Free	Found in 2019 (35)
• receiving prophylactic antibiotics when having an instrumental/surgical intervention (instrumental uterine evacuation, hysterectomy, laparotomy, laparoscopy)	100%		NA	NA	Yes (1 country)	NA	NA	NA	1 study	NA	Free	Found in 2019 (35)

Quality measures and corresponding indicators measured in AMoCo study	Targets	Data source	English Reliability	English Validity (construct and criterion)	Used and adapted in English Speaking African countries	French reliability	French validity (construct and criterion)	Used and adapted in French Speaking African countries	Used in research studies	Time in interview/w/in data collection	Price	References	
2- PROCESSES (Follow-up)													
PROVISION OF CARE: Application of post-abortion care evidence-based clinical guidelines (practices) – Follow-up:													
- <i>Infections (follow-up)</i> : Percentage of women	0%	MRR	NA	NA	Yes (5 countries)	NA	NA	Yes (5 countries)	1 study	NA	Free	Built from guidelines (15,16) Found in 2023 (50)	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> receiving antibiotics when there is no reported indication^e (inappropriate) 	100%		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Built from guidelines (15,16)	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> with tetanus vaccination status assessed & adequately managed 			NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA		
- <i>Anemia</i> : Percentage of women with anemia who were prescribed Iron/Folic acid at discharge			NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Found in 2019 (35) Found in 2023 (65,78)
- <i>Pain management</i> : Percentage of women having instrumental uterine evacuation who received adequate anesthesia (para cervical block, spinal anesthesia, general anesthesia)	100%		NA	NA	Yes, (1 country)	NA	NA	Yes, (1 country)	2 studies	NA	Free		
- <i>Contraception counselling</i> : Percentage of women having been counselled about contraception.	100%	NA	NA	Yes (7 countries)	NA	NA	Yes (5 countries)	6 studies	NA	Free	Found in 2019 (21,35) Found in 2023 (53,56,78,79)		

Quality measures and corresponding indicators measured in AMoCo study	Targets	Data source	English Reliability	English Validity (construct and criterion)	Used and adapted in English Speaking African countries	French reliability	French validity (construct and criterion)	Used and adapted in French Speaking African countries	Used in research studies	Time in interview/in data collection	Price	References
2- PROCESSES (Follow-up)												
EXPERIENCE OF CARE: Reported experience of post-abortion care:												
Percentage of women who reported that ^f												
- they were <i>given explanations</i> regarding care (UCSF PCMC scale & WHO-MCS-A question)	100 %	Quantitative patient survey	Cf. below	Cf. below	Yes (5 countries)	NA	NA	Yes (5 countries)	4 studies	NA	Free	Found in 2019 (14,40–42)
- they were <i>able to ask questions</i> during treatment (UCSF PCMC scale & WHO-MCS-A question)	100 %		NA	NA	Yes (5 countries)	NA	NA	Yes (5 countries)	1 study	NA	Free	Found in 2023 (48)
- they were <i>spoken to nicely</i> (WHO-MCS-A question)	100 %		NA	NA	Yes (5 countries)	NA	NA	Yes (5 countries)	1 study	NA	Free	Found in 2019 (14)
- they <i>received pain medication</i> (WHO-MCS-A question)	100 %		NA	NA	Yes (5 countries)	NA	NA	Yes (5 countries)	1 study	NA	Free	Found in 2023 (48)
- their <i>privacy was respected</i> all the time during physical examinations (UCSF PCMC scale)	100 %		<u>Cronbach</u> - 0,86 (full 30-items question naire), - 0,73 (communication) - 0,63 (respect/dignity), - 0,72 (support)	<u>Construct:</u> KMO = 0,91 <u>Criterion:</u> correlated with global measures of satisfaction	Yes (2 countries)	NA	NA	NA	3 studies	45 min for the full 30 questions questionnaire	Free	Found in 2019 (40–42)
- they had <i>very short or short waiting time</i> to see a provider (UCSF PCMC scale)	100 %											
- they were <i>asked about their feelings</i> (UCSF PCMC scale)	100 %											
- they <i>have been supported</i> by doctors or nurses about their <i>anxieties</i> and fears (UCSF PCMC scale)	100 %											

Quality measures and corresponding indicators measured in AMoCo study	Targets	Data source	English Reliability	English Validity (construct and criterion)	Used and adapted in English Speaking African countries	French reliability	French validity (construct and criterion)	Used and adapted in French Speaking African countries	Used in research studies	Time in interview/in data collection	Price	References
3- OUTCOMES												
PERSON-CENTERED OUTCOME												
<i>Good overall quality of the post-abortion care provided as perceived by the patient:</i> Percentage of women who reported that staff provided <u>best care all the time</u> (UCSF PCMC scale) ^f	100%	Quantitative patient survey	Cf. above	Cf. above	Yes (2 countries)	NA	NA	NA	3 studies	45 min for the full 30 questions questionnaire	Free	Found in 2019 (40–42)
HEALTH-RELATED OUTCOMES												
- <i>Abortion-related Mortality Index</i> : number of deaths/number of severe maternal outcome (SMO = near-miss cases [†] and deaths)	The lower, the better	MRR	NA	NA	Yes (5 countries)	NA	NA	Yes (5 countries)	WHO guidelines	NA	Free	Found in 2019 (43) Found in 2023 (49,79)
- <i>Risk of Healthcare-related abortion near-miss[†]</i> : number of women with Near-miss [†] happening >= 24h after presentation/total number of women presenting for abortion complications			NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes (4 countries)	1 Unpublished study	NA	Free	Found in 2023 (80)

^a Questions included in the Knowledge, Attitude Practice Behavior survey questionnaire among health professionals providing post-abortion care:

- Did your medical/clinical officer/midwifery/nursing school training include any content on post-abortion care? (yes/no)
- Access to post abortion care services is every woman's right (Agree/Neutral, Unsure/Disagree)

- According to the guidelines used in this health facility, how many micrograms of misoprostol are recommended to treat incomplete abortion in the 1st trimester with a first single oral dose?
 - o Correct answer: 600 micrograms
- According to the guidelines used in this health facility, what are the antibiotics to be given to treat septic abortion?
 - o Correct answer: Amoxicillin/Clavulanic acid or Amoxicillin + metronidazole or Amoxicillin/Clavulanic acid + Gentamycin
- Do you personally provide post-abortion care with Dilatation & Curettage at this facility? (yes/no)

^b List of the 27 extended comprehensive PAC signal functions used in the AMoCo study:

Comprehensive PAC Signal functions (from Campbell et al. (37))

Drugs, supplies, and services available for Post-Abortion Care

- Parenteral Uterotonics (at least 2 uterotonics with at least 1 parenteral available for PAC)
- Removal of retention products (manual or electric vacuum aspiration for PAC)
- Parenteral antibiotics
- Intravenous fluids
- Blood transfusion (with routine screening of donor blood for HIV, Hepatitis B, C & Syphilis)
- Surgical laparotomy capability (including hysterectomy)

Drugs, supplies, and services available for Post-abortion Contraception

- 3+ Modern short acting contraceptives
- 1+ Modern long-acting reversible contraceptives
- Contraception available 7/7

Infrastructure and Human Resources

- Facility open 24/7
- 1+ medical doctor on duty 24/7
- 3+ medical doctor registered and effectively working.

Additional signal functions to fulfill the extended capability to provide comprehensive PAC (from Compaore et al. (52))

Infrastructure

- Electricity available and functioning
- Generator available and functioning
- Refrigerator available and functioning
- Email/internet available and functioning.
- Incinerator available and functioning
- Water supply available and functioning
- Sewerage system available and functioning
- Referral capacity to refer patients if needed:
 - o Telephone/radio call available and functioning.
 - o Ambulance available and functioning

Guidelines, Equipment, and Human Resources

- Evidence based PAC guidelines available and accessible for clinicians.
- Clinical audits currently in use (regular mortality, morbidity and/or near-miss review)
- Critical care unit available and functioning (ICU or HDU) - As per the WHO near-miss approach definition(43), an intensive care unit (ICU) is a unit that provides 24-hour medical supervision (including continuous vital signs monitoring), mechanical ventilation (including oxygen) and continuous vaso-active drugs. The High Dependency Unit (HDU) is a unit with all those characteristics except the mechanical ventilation.
- Ultrasound available and functioning
- Biochemical/clinical laboratory available and functioning
- Anesthetist capacity on duty 24/7

^c A woman who needed a transfusion is defined by (MSF guidelines 2019(16)) a woman with:

- Hb \leq 5 g/dl, even if there are no signs of decompensation

- Hb $>$ 5 g/dl and $<$ 7 g/dl if there are signs of decompensation (lowest SBP \leq 90 mm Hg & pulse \geq 100 b/min) or sickle cell disease or severe malaria or serious bacterial infection or pre-existing heart disease.

^d Septic abortions include uterine infections, generalized peritonitis or severe systemic infections with genital origin and exclude extra-genital infections (malaria, urinary infections, etc.)

^e No indication of antibiotics includes: no documented infection, no instrumental/surgical procedure, no trauma/perforation (no evidence of cervix/vaginal mechanical injury at clinical examination, uterine perforation or other intra-abdominal perforation confirmed at laparotomy or at clinical examination), no notion of septic maneuver to induce abortion and no foreign body found in the vagina.

^f Questions included in the quantitative survey questionnaire among women who stayed at least overnight with abortion complications:

- During your stay at this hospital, were you given explanations regarding your care and treatment? (yes/no)
- Were you able to ask questions during the examination and treatment? (yes/no)
- Were you spoken to nicely? (yes/no)
- Did you receive pain medications during your hospital stay? (yes/no)
- During physical examinations (when the doctor was looking at private parts of your body) were you covered up (or given privacy in such a way only the doctor and nurses examining you could see you)? (Never/A few times/Most of the time/All the time/Not examined)
- How do you feel about the amount of time you waited (to see a healthcare provider)? Would you say it was: (Very short/Somewhat short/Somewhat long/Very long)
- Did the doctors and nurses at the facility talk to you about how you were feeling? (yes/no)
- Did the doctors, nurses or other staff at the facility support your anxieties and fears? (yes/no)
- Did you feel the doctors, nurses or other staff at the facility took the best care of you? (Never/A few times/Most of the time/All the time)

[†] Near- miss cases: women with organ dysfunction of either one or more of the following: cardiovascular, respiratory, renal, coagulation, hepatic, neurological or uterine dysfunction using WHO near-miss criteria(43,49).

MRR: Prospective Medical Records Review

NA: Not Available

PAC: Post-Abortion Care

QoC: Quality of Care

SMO: Severe Maternal Outcome = Near-miss cases + Deaths

UCSF PCMC scale: Person-Centered Maternity Care scale (University of California San Francisco)(40)

WHO-MCS-A: World Health Organization Multi-Countries Study on Abortion(14)

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